

Erratum and Full Retraction

The author identifies a critical error in the volume formula used for the disphenoid (isosceles tetrahedron) in the original manuscript. The correct formula, derived from the Cayley-Menger determinant, is:

$$V = \frac{\sqrt{2(a^2 + b^2 - c^2)(a^2 + c^2 - b^2)(b^2 + c^2 - a^2)}}{12}$$

Applying the correct formula to the tetrahedron with opposite edges (55, 104, 105) yields a volume of $34496\sqrt{2}$ (approximately 48790.6), which is not an integer. Consequently, the central claim that this tetrahedron is a perfect (integer-volume) Heronian tetrahedron, and that it establishes a minimal volume record, is retracted in full.

The author sincerely apologizes for the error and any confusion caused. The verifications of the tetrahedron's primitivity ($\gcd=1$), Heronian faces (area 2772), and acuteness remain valid.